

Klinisk forsøgsprotokol

Titel:

Hæmostatisk og Fibrinolytisk Analyse af Enoxaparin-Injektion versus Ufraktioneret Heparin som Post-CABG Thromboprophylakse

Forsøgsnummer: LITE

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Haemostatic and Fibrinolytic Analysis of Enoxaparin Injection versus Unfractionated Heparin as Post-CABG Thromboprophylaxis

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Trial phase: IV

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Abbreviations

AR	Adverse Reaction
AE	Adverse Event
AC	Anticoagulation
AMI	Acute myocardial infarction
ASA	Acetylsalicylic acid
CABG	Coronary Artery Bypass Graft surgery
CRF	Case Report Form
ECC	Extracorporeal circulation
ICH-GCP guidelines	International Conference on Harmonization-Good Clinical Practice
IV	Intravenous
LMWH	Low molecular weight heparin
NOAC	Non-vitamin K oral anticoagulation
PI	Principal Investigator
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
SC	Subcutaneous
SD	Standard deviation
SI	Sponsor Investigator
SmPC	Summary of Product Characteristics
SUSAR	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction
UFH	Unfractionated Heparin

Protocol summary

Title

Haemostatic and Fibrinolytic Analysis of Enoxaparin Injection versus Unfractionated Heparin as Post-CABG Thromboprophylaxis

Study design

Prospective, blinded (to the coagulation lab), randomised, comparative, single-centre study with three treatment groups, randomised on the first post-operative day:

1. Acetylsalicylic acid, orally
2. Subcutaneous low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) injection + acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), orally
3. Intravenous unfractionated heparin (UFH) + acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), orally

Blood samples will be taken 1-3 hours prior to administration of trial product and 4-6 hours after administration of trial product every day during the first 4 post-operative days. Five millilitres of blood will be sampled each time, used in TEG[®] and Multiplate[®] analyses. Blood will be stored for 2 months after analysis and then destroyed.

Background

Coronary bypass graft surgery (CABG) constitutes a considerable intervention with marked effect on the patient's various organ systems and stress on the organism as a whole. In particular, the haemostasis –and fibrinolysis – is affected by the use of extracorporeal circulation (ECC) and multi-pharmacology both during and after surgery.¹

Many factors affect the haemostatic system in heart patients undergoing CABG: liver function, thrombocyte activity, endothelial function, and pharmacology.²

In the literature, it has not been elucidated how these factors converge on and affect the patient haemostasis after heart surgery. Also, a large observational trial has shown poor evidence for the effect of various thromboprophylactic interventions specifically during heart surgery.³

Therefore, it seems relevant to address and investigate the haemostatic system in heart surgery patients with different postoperative thromboprophylactic regimens.

Aim

The primary aim of this study is quantification of any effect of the different thromboprophylactic strategies on the haemostatic system, demonstrated by TEG and Multiplate in each of the 3 treatment groups.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis will be tested:

There are no differences in the 3 treatment groups concerning the haemostatic and fibrinolytic system, measured by TEG and Multiplate.

The null-hypothesis will be tested against the alternative by construction 2-sided 95 % confidence intervals of the average differences in TEG R-time and Multiplate ASPI between the 3 groups.

Outcomes

The primary outcomes are:

- TEG-analysis: reaction time (R), minutes
- Multiplate: ASPI test, units

The secondary outcomes are:

- Bleeding complications:
 - SAGM-usage
 - Plasma usage
 - Thrombocyt usage
 - Re-operation for bleeding
 - Gastrointestinal bleeding
- Thromboembolic complications:
 - Central nerve damage
 - Reoperation for myocardial ischaemia
 - Acute myocardial infarction (AMI)
- Number of patients in each randomisation group with unexpected complications
- Other TEG and Multiplate parameters

Study duration

Participants will be included over the course of 12 months. For each participant, the duration is the first 4 post-operative days.

Study population

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients referred to elective CABG in the Department of Thoracic Surgery, Rigshospitalet.

Exclusion criteria:

- Age <18 years
- Re-operations
- Emergency operations (< 24 hours)
- No pausation of thrombocyte inhibitors (e.g. ASA or Clopidogrel) 4 days prior to surgery
- Patient needing other thrombocyte inhibitors than ASA
- Weight <60 kg or >110 kg (due to UFH protein binding)
- No informed consent
- Treatment with vitamin-K-antagonists or NOAC
- Known liver failure
- Known kidney insufficiency
- Pregnant patients
- Participation in other medical trials
- Allergy to trial product
- Known haemorrhagic diathesis

Medication dosage

Each participant in all groups receives 75 mg of ASA once daily starting on the first post-operative day.

The 2nd and 3rd randomisation group then receives either 40 mg Klexane once daily for 4 days or 100 mg/ml infusion Heparin "LEO" corresponding to a daily dose of 7 IE/kg.

Concomitant medication

The following medications are incompatible with trial participation:

- Other heparins than the trial product
- Other types of ASA or nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID)

Safety evaluation and reporting

A safety evaluation will be completed for the patients experiencing any *Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction* (SUSAR).

The patient group in this study generally experience many *Adverse Events* (AEs) of which most will likely be unrelated to trial product. For this reason, the registered AEs will only be known AEs to the trial product, such as bleeding complications or thromboembolic complications. Each patient will be followed up within 30 days after hospital discharge to identify AEs of this type. All these relevant AEs will be reported as secondary outcomes and included in the analysis.

Adverse effects, risks and disadvantages

The trial participants' main disadvantages due to participation is the extraction of one extra blood sample each day in comparison to standard treatment. Also, the continuous infusion for one of the groups is not standard treatment.

Common adverse effects from the infusion include reactions at injection site, increase in liver biomarkers, decrease in thrombocyte count, and bleeding tendency with higher doses. Rare adverse effects include allergic reactions varying from skin rash to anaphylaxis.

Statistical analysis

Sample size

There are currently no data known to this group on the effect of the trial medication in the three heart surgery trial groups on TEG and Multiplate analyses. For this reason, the relevant assumptions for a power calculation are missing.

Instead, we estimate that 20 patients in each trial group will be sufficient for an explorative study on the medications' effect on TEG and Multiplate analyses. This can form the basis for another, larger trial, potentially with focus on clinical outcomes.

Data analysis

The 3 groups will be compared with a repeated mixed model with 3 variables (group, time, and time*group). Significant differences between group and group*time will be followed by post-hoc t-tests (if data are normally distributed) or Mann-Whitney U test (if data are not normally distributed) comparisons for each time point. Each of the 3 intervention groups will be analysed with a repeated mixed model for changes over time (only including the time variable) and post-hoc paired t-test / Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test. The

groups will be compared at baseline with t-test / Mann-Whitney U test as well as Chi-square test / Fisher's exact test. P values < 0.05 will be considered statistically significant

Participating countries

Denmark

Trial location

Department of Thoracic Surgery, Rigshospitalet

Ethical considerations

This study will follow the ICH-GCP-guidelines, the Helsinki declaration, and any regulatory demands. Informed consent will be required from trial participants before any study activity, including blood sampling, changes in treatment regimens and so on.

The protocol will be registered and approved at relevant authorities (the National Committee on Health Research Ethics, Danish Health Authority, and Danish Data Protection Agency)

Informed consent

Patients will be recruited the day before their surgery by the trial administrators. Recruiting will be done in a room without others present and preferably in the presence of next of kin. In case next of kin or another assessor needed by the patient cannot be present at the time of informing the patient, the recruitment time will naturally be postponed. After confirmation of wish to participate, written material with relevant participant information will be handed out.

A signed copy of the informed consent will be stored in the patient journal. Information regarding trial participation will be delivered in a fashion suited for the patients' expected comprehension level. In this information, it will be underlined that participation is voluntary and that withdrawal from the trial is always possible without needing any explanation. Also, it will be underlined that eventual drop-out will not affect the patient's treatment in any way.

Monitoring

This study will be monitored by the GCP unit at Bispebjerg Hospital to ensure that the protocol is adhered to. This includes, but is not limited to, patient safety and rights, adherence to ICH-GCP guidelines, and adherence to other agreements and restrictions, as well as ensuring data authenticity and completeness.

Trial safety and patient eligibility for the study will be monitored using relevant blood samples, medical records, and medication history. Blood samples for monitoring of outcomes and safety will be analysed at the Blood Bank at Rigshospitalet.

Funding

This project will be sought externally funded, however, internal funding will be secured until relevant scholarships or other funding is achieved. The National Committee on Health Research Ethics will be informed as soon as possible in the case of external funding.

Publication

Negative as well as inconclusive results will be sought published in an international journal. In case this goal is not realised, then national journals will be applied to.

All contributors will be noted as authors, though adhering to the Vancouver Declaration. Actual order of authors will be detailed later; however, Ulver Spangsberg Lorenzen will be first author regardless.

Introduction

Background

A heart surgery procedure such as a coronary artery artery bypass graft surgery (CABG) is an extensive surgical intervention with considerable effect on the operated patient's organ systems. During the procedure that is substantial stress of the whole organism and thus all organ functions, especially on the haemostatic system. Also, the use of extracorporeal circulation (ECC) and multipharmacology affects the haemostatic system during and after the surgery.^{1,2}

A proper balance needs to be maintained between a functioning haemostasis on the one hand to prevent bleeding from anastomoses and from internal organs (especially cerebral and gastrointestinal bleeding), and on the other hand sufficient protection against thromboembolic complications.

The latter includes deep vein thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism (PE), cerebral thromboembolic events, and post-operative graft thrombosis that can lead to perioperative myocardial infarction, heart insufficiency, or death.⁴

In an elective CABG, the thrombocyte inhibitors are usually paused 5 days prior to surgery to reduce perioperative bleeding. During the procedure, the patient needs to be fully anticoagulated, due to the use of the heart-lung-machine, using unfractionated heparin (for an ACT > 450 seconds), and by the end of the procedure, this heparinisation is reverted with the antidote protamine sulfate (for an ACT < 140 seconds).⁵ When the drain production is decreasing post surgery, the treatment with thrombocyte inhibitors (typically acetylsalicylic acid (ASA)) is reinstated – routinely 6 hours after surgery, and for the following 4 days the patient is administered low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) once daily.⁶

Rationale

Many factors affect the haemostatic system in heart patients during and after CABG: liver function, endothelial function, and medication administered during hospitalisation.²

In the literature, it has not been elucidated how these factors converge on and affect the patient haemostasis after heart surgery. Also, a large observational trial has shown poor evidence for the effect of various thromboprophylactic interventions specifically during heart surgery.³

Therefore, it seems relevant to address and investigate the haemostatic system in heart surgery patients with different postoperative thromboprophylactic regimens.

This project attacks this problem by investigating the haemostasis in the post-operative setting in heart surgery patients, who have gone through an elective CABG, and receives one of three different post-operative antithrombotic regimens: Patients only treated with 75 mg ASA once daily post surgery. This treatment regimen has been used for many years at Rigshospitalet, but was recently changed on empirical to regimen '2' (underneath) per January 1st 2014.

1. Patients that in addition to ASA are treated with LMWH (Klexane 40 mg) once daily for 4 days as a subcutaneous injection. This treatment regimen was started at Rigshospitalet January 1st 2014
2. Patients that in addition to ASA are treated with unfractionated heparin as a continuous infusion for 4 days.

Knowledge of the precise effects of antithrombotic treatment in post-CABG patients is an important step in prevention and reduction of peri-operative complications.

With the introduction of the cell-based coagulation model, analyses done on plasma alone – such as prothrombin (PT), INR, and APTT – has become less important in the evaluation of the patient's haemostatic system.⁷ For this reason, full blood analyses such as TEG/ROTEM has been made the standard for the evaluation of peri-operative haemostasis.

TEG/ROTEM with heparin-neutralising additives can be used to precisely estimate the patient's haemostatic balance and identify eventual coagulopathies from heparin administration.⁷ Another factor with influence on the coagulation is the endothelial function, which can be monitored with TEG, since endothelial damage releases heparan sulphate and soluble thrombomodulin, which are anticoagulating with prolonged R-time.⁸

Multiplate analysis is, like TEG/ROTEM, a full blood analysis that can be used to measure patient thrombocyte function. Multiplate has in several studies been correlated to relevant clinical outcomes, such as stent-thrombosis after PCI in coronary disease,⁹ and is used to monitor patients treated with thrombocyte inhibitor – such as the patients in this trial.

Analysis methods

TEG®

TEG analysis, a type of thromboelastography, assesses the haemostasis from its viscoelastic properties under low shear stress conditions. The product creates a real-time graphical visualisation of the haemostatic process, from which relevant values can be extrapolated, including time until coagulation initiation (reaction time, *R*), maximum amplitude (*MA*), coagulation kinetics (α), and lysis of the coagulum (Ly30)¹⁰.

The method is relatively simple and is carried out by measuring the resistance to movement in full blood after addition of activators. This resistance is measured by oscillating the cup containing full blood around a measuring pin submerged in the blood.

The method is quick (about 15 minutes) and is therefore often used in traumatology, where specifically *MA* has been related to important clinical outcomes.¹¹

Outcomes:

- **Reaction time**, *R*, is measured in minutes, and it represents the initiation phase of coagulation. At this moment, fibrin precipitation happens alongside filopodia generation in the thrombocytes.
- **Angle**, α , is measured in degrees, and it represents coagulation kinetics. It visualises the 'thrombin burst', which follows activation of Factor X and leads fibrin polymerisation.
- **Maximum amplitude**, *MA*, is measured in millimetres and represents the maximum clot strength.
- **Funktional fibrinogen maximum amplitude**, *MAff*, is measured in millimetres and represents the maximum clot strength conferred by fibrinogen alone.
- **Fibrinolysis**, Ly30, is measured in percent and represents clot break down.

Multiplate®

Multiplate® is a thrombocyte function analysis, which measures thrombocyte aggregation in full blood. It is able to identify increased bleeding, especially in patients in thrombocyte inhibitor treatment. This method, which is a type of multiple electrode aggregometry (MEA), rests on deposition and aggregation of thrombocytes around electrodes submerged in the analysed full blood. These electrodes measure electrical impedance, which is converted to an arbitrary unit. This process is initiated by manual addition of activator

to the analysed blood. The result graphically describes the thrombocytes' aggregation capacity and is expressed as the area under the curve (AUC), thus multiplying aggregation units times minutes. In addition, the maximum thrombocyte aggregation and the aggregation velocity can be extrapolated¹².

Outcomes:

- **ASPI test** is measured in Units, U, and is carried out by addition of arachidonic acid to the blood, which is converted by the COX-1-enzyme into thromboxane, which again activates thrombocyte aggregation. Arachidonic acid is on its own not thrombocyte activating, which is why the test is specific for COX-1 activity and can be used to measure the effects of thrombocyte inhibitors such as acetylsalicylic acid.
- **TRAP test** is measured in Units, U, and is carried out by addition of thrombin receptor activating peptide (TRAP). This test analyses thrombocyte activation triggered by the thrombin receptor – without any addition of actual thrombin, which would otherwise lead to fibrin polymerisation.
- **ADP test** is measured in Units, U, and is carried out by addition of adenosine phosphate, which activates the thrombocytes via the ADP receptor.
- **RISTO test** is measured in Units, U, and is carried out by addition of ristocetin; an antibiotic, which leads to complex formation with Willebrandt Factor (vWF), which then binds to the thrombocytes and stimulates aggregation via Glycoprotein Ib. This test can therefore help detect vWF-deficiency.

Aims

Primary

- Quantification of any effects of different post-operative treatment regimens on the patient haemostasis, measured by TEG and Multiplate in the 3 trial groups.

Secondary

- Registration of symptomatic thrombo-embolic complications in the 3 groups within 30 days.
- Registration of clinical bleeding episodes in the 3 trial groups within 30 days.

Outcomes

Primary outcomes

- TEG analysis: reaction time (R), min
- Multiplate: ASPI test, U

Secondary outcomes

These will be registered by a standard data registration form for heart surgery and by telephone contact to the patient 30 days post-operatively:

- Bleeding complications:
 - SAGM-usage
 - Plasma usage
 - Thrombocyte usage
 - Re-operation for bleeding
 - Gastrointestinal bleeding
- Thromboembolic complications:

- Central nerve damage
- Re-operation for myocardial ischemia
- Acute myocardial infarction
- Number of patients in each randomisation group experiencing sudden unexpected complications
- Other analytical outcomes (see Analysis methods, page 12) apart from the primary outcomes.

Study design

Sixty consecutive patients will be included, all planned for elective CABG surgery. All patients are heparinised during surgery, reverted with protamine sulphate and started in ASA-treatment 6 hours post-operatively, following internal recommendations^{13,14}. All patients receive ASA 75 mg once daily for lifetime following surgery.

The study is designed as a prospective, semi-blinded (in the case of the laboratory), randomised, comparative, and single-centre trial with 3 treatment groups, randomised on the first post-operative day:

1. ASA-treatment alone (75 mg once daily)
2. Subcutaneous Klexane[®] injection once daily for the first 4 post-operative days (in addition to ASA)
3. Intravenous heparin infusion (7 IU/kg/h) for the first 4 post-operative days (in addition to ASA)

Blood samples will be taken 1-3 hours prior to trial product administration (usually at 5-9 am) and 4-6 hours after administration (usually at 1-3 pm) every day for the first 4 post-operative days. The 3 groups are not blinded after surgery, but the blood samples are sent blinded to the laboratory at the blood bank. Each sample is 5 ml used for the TEG[®]- and Multiplate[®]-analysis. After the analysis, the blood samples are stored for 2 months according to standard procedure, after which they are destroyed.

The trial participants' preoperative EUROSCORE (see **Fejl! Henvisningskilde ikke fundet.**, page Fejl! Bogmærke er ikke defineret.) will be used as a measure for confounding. The trial participants are randomised by use of opaque envelopes with randomly distributed numbers. The allocated trial product is registered in the participant's Case Report Form (CRF) with inclusion of the batch number in the respective field. In case of drop-out, a new patient will be included to ensure 20 trial participants in each group.

Study population

The study population consists of all patients referred to CABG-surgery at the Department of Thoracical Surgery (Rigshospitalet) that fulfil the inclusion and exclusion criteria. To our knowledge, no data exists on the potential effects of the trial product in the 3 groups, and thus, no power calculation can be completed. This protocol describes a pilot study including 60 patients (20 in each trial arm). We estimate that this will be sufficient to explore the trial products' effect on TEG and Multiplate parameters.

Qualification for the trial

Inclusion criteria

Patients referred for elective CABG surgery at the department of Thoracical Surgery at Rigshospitalet.

Exclusion criteria

- Age under 18 years
- Re-operations
- Emergency surgery (< 24 hours)
- Improper pausation of thrombocyte inhibitors prior to surgery
- Need for other thrombocyte inhibitors than ASA
- Body weight below 60 kg or over 110 kg (due to UFH protein binding)
- No informed consent
- Treatment with vitamin-K-antagonists and NOAC
- Known liver failure
- Known kidney insufficiency
- Pregnancy
- Participation in other medicine trials
- Allergy to trial products
- Known haemorrhagic diathesis

Trial products

Description

Information on trial products has been collected from product resumes available on www.produktresume.dk

Acetylsalicylic acid

The product used by the department is sold as "Hjertemagnyl" and produced by Takeda Pharma. It is used as a basic thromboprophylaxis after CABG surgery. The mechanism of action is inhibition of the thrombocytes' cyclooxygenase, whereby thromboxane A2 production is decreased. Thromboxane A2 plays an important part in thrombocyte activation, which is why inhibition leads to increased bleeding time and inhibited thrombus formation.

The effect on the thrombocyte is irreversible due to irreversible binding and no protein synthesis in the thrombocytes, and the treatment effect continues 24-48 timer after cessation.

As post-CABG thromboprophylaxis, ASA is usually administered perorally and is absorbed completely from the gastrointestinal tract.

Enoxaparine

The product used by the department is sold as "Klexane" and produced by Sanofi. It is made by a controlled partial depolymerisation of unfractionated heparin extracted from porcine intestinal mucosa. Its average molecular weight is approximately 4,500 Dalton. It is used as a standard thromboprophylaxis against deep vein thrombosis after CABG surgery at Rigshospitalet. It is a low molecular weight heparin, and its

mechanism of action is facilitating complex binding between antithrombin III and factor Xa, which – among other effects – mediates the antithrombotic effect. The medication has a high anti-Xa activity, but a low anti-IIa activity.

As post-CABG thromboprophylaxis, Enoxaparin is usually administered as a subcutaneous injection.

Unfractionated Heparin

The medication used in this trial is sold as Heparin “LEO” and is produced by Leo Pharma. It is likewise from porcine origin and consists of a heterogenous mixture of polysaccharide chains.

Unfractionated Heparin is used as standard procedure during operative surgery with high risk of thrombosis such as CABG with heart-lung machine. It is also used in acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction.

Like the low molecular weight heparins, it works by potentiation of the antithrombin-III inhibition mediated by Factor Xa and IIa. Due to a different complex binding, the effect on Factor IIa is greater than that of the low molecular weight heparins.

Unfractionated heparin is usually administered as an intravenous bolus or continuous infusion.

Dosage and administration

Trial participants will be randomised to one of three groups:

Treatment group 1: Acetylsalicylic acid orally

One tablet acetylsalicylic acid of 75 mg is given once daily at 9 AM from the first post-operative day.

Treatment group 2: Acetylsalicylic acid orally + Enoxaparin subcutant

One tablet acetylsalicylic acid of 75 mg is given once daily at 9 AM from the first post-operative day.

Simultaneously, one subcutaneous injection of 100 mg/ml enoxaparin sodium is given for a dosage of 40 mg 1 once daily at 9 AM throughout the first 4 postoperative days.

Treatment group 3: Acetylsalicylic acid orally + Unfractionated Heparin via intravenous infusion

One tablet acetylsalicylic acid of 75 mg is given once daily at 9 AM from the first post-operative day.

At the first post-operative day, an infusion pump will be started, administering 7 IU/kg/hour throughout the first 4 postoperative days.

The pump will be regularly controlled for any interruptions.

Dosage rationale

The dosages of acetylsalicylic acid and enoxaparin are chosen from the standard procedures and the respective medication product resumes.

The dosage and administration form (infusion pump) of Unfractionated Heparin is chosen from the medication's high protein binding (99%) and its short half life.

Side effects and risks

The side effects of the trial medication are divided by frequency: very common (>10 %), common (1-10 %), uncommon (0.1-1 %), rare (0.01-0.1 %), and very rare (<0.01 %).

Acetylsalicylic acid

The following side effects have been found with acetylsalicylic acid:

Blood and lymphatic system

- Common: increased bleeding tendency
- Rare: thrombocytopenia, granulocytosis, aplastic anemia

Immune system

- Rare: hypersensitivity reactions, angioedema, allergic edema, anaphylactic reactions

Nerve system

- Rare: Intracranial hemorrhage

Vascular diseases

- Rare: Hemorrhagic vasculitis

Airways

- Uncommon: Rhinitis, dyspnea
- Rare: Broncospasm, asthma attacks

Reproductive system

- Rare: menorrhagy

Gastrointestinal canal

- Common: Dyspepsia
- Rare: Severe gastrointestinal hemorrhage, nausea, emesis

Skin and subcutaneous tissues

- Rare: Steven-Johnson's syndrome, Lyell's syndrome, purpura, erythema nodosum, erythema multiforme

Enoxaparine

The following side effects have been found with enoxaparine in surgical patients:

Blood and lymphatic system

- Very common: Thrombocytosis
- Common: Thrombocytopenia

Immune system

- Common: allergisc reactions
- Rare: hypersensitivity reactions, angioedema, allergic edema, anaphylactic reactions

Nerve system

- Rare: Intracranial hemorrhage

Vascular diseases

- Very common: Bleeding, haematoma
- Rare: Retroperitoneal bleeding

Gastrointestinal canal

- Very common: Increase in lever parameters

Skin and subcutaneous tissues

- Common: Urticaria, pruritus, erythema
- Uncommon: Bullous dermatitis

Metabolism

- Uncommon: Hyperkalemia

General symptoms

- Uncommon: Injection site reactions

Unfractionated Heparin

The following side effects have been found with unfractionated Heparin:

Blood and lymphatic system

- Uncommon: Non-immune heparin associated thrombocytopenia (type I)

Immune system

- Uncommon: heparin induced thrombocytopenia (type II), anaphylactic reactions, hypersensitivity

Vascular diseases

- Very common: bleeding, haematoma

Skin and subcutaneous tissues

- Common: Erythema
- Uncommon: Skin necrosis, rash, urticaria, pruritus

Metabolism

- Common: Increased liver parameters
- Uncommon: Hyperkalemia
- Uncommon: Activated partial thromboplastin time prolonged beyond therapeutic interval

Bones, joints, muscles and connective tissue

- Uncommon: Osteoporosis (with longterm treatment)

General symptoms

- Uncommon: Injection site reactions

Preparation of trial medication

Commercially available acetylsalicylic acid oral tablets and Enoxaparine, "Klexane", 100 mg/ml ampules will be taken from the department's standard supplement for use in the trial. Additionally, infusion pumps will be purchased for the continuous infusions of Unfractionated Heparine.

Principal investigator is responsible for the preparation of trial medication. No drugs in this trial will be administered after expiry date.

Handling and storage

Trial medication will only be administered as described in this clinical trial protocol. Only trial participants included in the trial will receive the trial medication. All current legislation will be adhered to in relation to administration of trial medication. Only authorised personnel may administer trial medication. All trial medication will be kept in a safe storage with limited access only to authorised personnel and kept in accordance with the specific requirements of the trial medications' product resumé.

Trial medication responsibility

Principal investigator is committed to ensuring that relevant documentation on trial medication is collected and kept updated throughout the trial duration and in accordance with current legislation.

Trial medication compliance is ensured by the presence of either principal investigator or project nurses during administration of trial medication and by frequent monitoring of the continuous infusions.

Concurrent medication

Approved medication

Trial participants may take any medication necessary for their treatment except for the medications mentioned below. Concurrent medication, which is beyond the standard treatment in CABG patients, is noted on the relevant case report form. This information will include generic name, administration form, dosis, dosage start, and indication.

Incompatible medication

- Other heparins than the trial medication
- Other acetylsalicylic acid medication than the trial medication

Trial participant's completion and withdrawal

Completion of trial

When a trial participant has completed the trial, the principal investigator will fill out the completion formula in the respective case report form.

Withdrawal from trial

Participation is voluntary and trial participants can always withdraw from the trial without further explanation and without eventual drop-out affecting the participant's treatment in any way. Likewise, principal investigator can withdraw participants from the trial if the need arises, e.g., due to new disease, need for re-operation, adverse events, treatment failure, or failure to adhere to the protocol.

Upon withdrawal of consent, the principal investigator will discuss the possibility of continuation of the participant's antithrombotic treatment in the post-operative care, so that the patient's health can be ensured by adequate treatment. If supplied by the participant, principal investigator will note the reason for withdrawal in the patient's case report form.

Adverse events

Definition

Adverse Event

An *Adverse Event* (AE) is defined by the *International Conference on Harmonisation Guideline for Good Clinical Practice* (ICH-GCP) as:

"... any untoward medical occurrence in a subject or clinical investigation subject administered a pharmaceutical product and that does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment." ¹⁵

A *non-serious* AE adverse event in this trial will be registered in the patient's medical record from informed consent and until hospital discharge.

Worsening of an existing medical condition should be considered an AE if there is an increased severity, frequency, or duration of the condition, or an association with significantly worse outcome. Already present. Pre-existing medical conditions that do not worsen are not considered Adverse Events.

The trial investigator undertakes review of test results and assesses, whether there is a change in the trial participant compared to before participation in the study. These should also assess whether an abnormal value in a trial participant represents an AE, or whether it is a change in laboratory values without clinical significance. A change in laboratory values that leads to treatment or adjustment of previous treatment beyond what is usually expected is considered to be an AE and is recorded as such.

Serious Adverse Event

Et *Serious Adverse Event* (SAE) er defineret som et AE, der enten er fatalt, er livstruende, kræver hospitalisering (minimum én nat), kræver forlængelse af forhenværende hospitalisering, resulterer i handicap, resulterer i en fødselsdefekt or på anden måde er en betydelig medicinsk fare. Hvis den nævnte interventioner er en del af standard procedure, anses helbredsproblemet ikke som et *Serious Adverse Event*. Hvis en komplikation til en sådan standard procedure opfylder et af ovenstående kriterier, skal denne komplikation rapporteres som et SAE.

A Serious Adverse Event (SAE) is defined as an AE that is either fatal, life-threatening, requires hospitalization (minimum one night), requires extension of previous hospitalization, results in disability, results in a birth defect, or is otherwise significant medical hazard. If the intervention mentioned is part of the standard procedure, the health problem is not considered a Serious Adverse Event. If a complication of such a standard procedure meets one of the above criteria, this complication should be reported as an SAE.

Non-serious Adverse Event

Defined as any AE that does not fulfil the criteria for an SAE.

Adverse Reaction

An *Adverse Reaction* (AR) is an unpleasant and unintended reaction to a drug from the trial, which is considered to have causality to the treatment.

Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction

A Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction (SUSAR) is defined as a serious AR, whose course or severity is not in accordance with the product summary of the trial medication.

Reporting

This patient group generally experiences many Adverse Events (AEs), where a considerable proportion of these will probably be unrelated to the trial medication. Therefore, only the AEs known for the trial medicine, such as bleeding complications and thromboembolic complications, are recorded. All participants

will be followed up by telephone 30 days after discharge from the ward to identify AEs of this type in the follow-up process. All these relevant AEs will subsequently be reported as secondary efficacy measures and thus included in the analysis. All SAEs regardless of assessed relevance will be recorded.

A relevant AE that is either reported by the trial participant or observed by the trial leader will be described with concise medical terminology and, if possible, with a specific diagnosis. The severity, duration, predictability, and causal relationship of this AE will be described according to WHO recommendations.

Any relevant AE and SAE will be investigated at follow-up to determine the course until the outcome of the patient's event is resolved.

Blinding and SUSAR

In the event of a SUSAR, the treatment course will be interrupted, and the incident reported to the relevant authorities, including the Danish Health Authority and the Ethics Committee, as soon as possible and no later than 7 days after for fatal or life-threatening SUSARs or no later than 15 days after for all other SUSARs. Since the samples are sent blinded to the laboratory, and since the treatment regimen is known, a possible SUSAR will probably not cause the need to break the blinding, unless it seems imperative due to the circumstances. Whether it is a SAR or a SUSAR will be assessed based on the respective side effect profiles of the attached product summaries.

Pregnancy

Pregnancy is considered an exclusion criterion in this study, and the majority of the patient group will not be of childbearing age. If a potential trial participant is of childbearing age, urine HCG will be measured to rule out a possible unknown or undisclosed pregnancy.

Overdosage

Overdosage of ASA, Klexane and UFH can cause bleeding tendency. These are recognized medicines for the right indications, and the doses are below a level that could cause substantially increased risk. It is therefore not considered necessary to monitor the dose beyond the usual standard care.

Data analysis and statistical consideration

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis will be tested:

There is no difference in the 3 treatment groups on the haemostatic and fibrinolytic system measured with TEG and Multiplate.

The null hypothesis will be tested against the alternative by constructing a two-sided 95% confidence interval of the mean differences in TEG R time and Multiplate ASPI U between the three groups.

Study design considerations

Sample size

There is currently no data with TEG combined with Multiplate that is 100% relevant for power calculation for this exploratory pilot trial. However, significant changes in TEG values have previously been demonstrated in our group in 8+8 surgical patients treated with drugs that induce fibrinolysis (Prof. Johansson, personal communication). Since the patients in the present study are also surgical and treated with a drug that affects haemostasis, we estimate that monitoring 20 patients per group and with blood samples taken across 4 days will give us the necessary data to compare the effect of the various interventions on haemostasis partly between the groups as well as between the different test times, based on the fact that the study is exploratory. With this, the present study will provide the necessary knowledge to design a clinically relevant study with patient number based on a qualified power calculation.

Data analysis

The three groups are compared with a repeated mixed model with three variables (group, time and time*group). Significant differences between group and group*time will be followed by post-hoc t-tests (if data are normally distributed) or Mann-Whitney U test (if data are not normally distributed) comparisons at each time point. Each of the 3 intervention groups will be analyzed with a Repeated Mixed Model for changes over time (only including a time variable) and post-hoc paired t-test/Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. The groups will be compared to baseline with t-test/Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test/Fisher's Exact Test. P-value < 0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Trial administration

Practical feasibility

The expertise relevant to the study is fully available at the RT and Blood Bank department at Rigshospitalet. Approx. 800 isolated CABG procedures annually in the department. The Thoracic Surgery Department RT and the Blood Bank at Rigshospitalet have both given the necessary commitment for the study to be carried out.

Time schedule

Testing and establishment of method: Spring 2015

Start of studies and inclusion: Summer 2015

End of data collection: Autumn 2015

Data analysis and article writing: Winter 2015

Notification of authorities

The project is reported as a trial to the Ethics Committee, Capital Region.

The project is reported to the Danish Health Authority.

The project is notified to the Danish Data Protection Agency and the Act on the Processing of Personal Information is complied with.

Monitorin

This study will be monitored by the GCP unit at Bisbebjerg Hospital to ensure that the protocol's regulations are adhered to. This will include, but not be limited to: patient safety and rights, compliance with ICH-GCP guidelines, compliance with the approved protocol, compliance with other agreements or orders, as well as ensuring the authenticity and completeness of the data.

The safety of the study and the patients' qualification for the study are monitored with relevant blood tests, in-depth anamnesis and journal entries as well as entries in relevant medication lists. Blood samples for monitoring efficacy measures and safety will be analysed in the blood bank at Rigshospitalet.

Funding/financial support

The project is sought to be financed by an external fund, with internal funding obtained until a relevant scholarship or the like have been obtained. The Scientific Ethics Committee will be notified as soon as possible if external support is obtained.

Result dissemination

Negative as well as inconclusive and positive results will be sought published in an international journal. If this is not successful, attempts will be made with national journals and presentation at international or national conferences.

All participants are included as authors, provided that the rules are observed according to the Vancouver declaration. Final order will be agreed later, however, with Ulver Spangsberg Lorenzen as first author.

Informed consent

Patients are recruited the day before the operation by the trial managers. The recruitment takes place in a room with no one else is present, preferably together with patient relatives. If relatives or other desired assistants cannot be present at the information interview, the meeting will be postponed as far as possible. After confirmation of the desire to participate, written material containing relevant participant information is provided, in which, among other things, the possibility of co-sitters at any later meetings is specified.

A copy of a completed and signed consent form is kept in the patient's medical record. Information about participation in the project is given in a form that is adapted to the patient's expected level of understanding. In this information, it is emphasised that participation is voluntary, can always be withdrawn without further explanation and that any drop-out from the project does not affect the patient's treatment in any way during and after the operation.

Disclosure of information from the patient record

Data collection for this study will be carried out from electronic medical records, data registration form papers, and laboratory results - all data will be in Rigshospitalet's general databases (*Opus Workplace*). Data from subjects needed in the statistical analysis and for reporting will be entered into a validated database or data system. Handling of clinical data will be carried out in accordance with current standards and data protection procedures and approved by the Danish Data Protection Agency. This database will be physically destroyed 1 year after the trial's publication in collaboration with the IT department.

The attending physician passes on information from the patient record. These include information for calculating the operative mortality risk (EuroSCORE), which is calculated from patient-related factors (e.g., age, sex, cardiopulmonary status, and previous disease), cardiac risk factors (e.g., unstable angina, reduced ventricular function, and pulmonary hypertension) and surgery-related risk factors (e.g., emergency surgery and other heart surgery); and includes information on operative and postoperative complications.

Scientific, social, and ethical perspectives

In national and international guidelines, there exist no clear recommendations for anticoagulant treatment after CABG surgery, apart from treatment with ASA (unchanged for all patients included in the study). There is no validated knowledge about the function of the coagulation system and the fibrinolytic system after CABG surgery. This is to be assessed in this study. The results will hopefully provide more information about this so that we can in future treat patients based on evidence in this area.

Only well-known drugs (ASA, LMWH, and UFH) will be used in this trial.

During the project, 2 - 4 extra blood samples are taken on all patients. The patients in the UFH group must have a continuous infusion for 4 days and maintain CVK for one extra day.

The study will comply with the ICH-GCP guidelines, the Declaration of Helsinki, and any other regulatory requirements that may be imposed. All subjects must give informed consent before any activity related to the study will be carried out, including blood sampling, change of treatment regimens, and the like.

The protocol is notified to the relevant authorities (The National Ethics Committee, the Danish Health Authority, the Danish Data Protection Agency) before the project is started.

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